

DEVELOPING AFRICAN INDIGENOUS CARTOON SERIES FOR PEDAGOGICAL APPLICATIONS

Lilian Okoro, Ph.D

Department of Theatre and Media Studies, University of Calabar, Nigeria

E-mail: paciafrica@yahoo.com

Abstract

It has been observed that very few cartoon series based on African culture are available for African children. Also there are even fewer cartoon series embedded with significant recurrent imagery drawn from the Africa milieu created strictly for instructive purposes. In contrast with this scenario, a vast number of western cartoon series flood the African media network and play key roles in modelling African children towards the ideals of the west. While it has been observed that children subscribe more to cartoon programmes, they also follow and emulate the presentations very closely. It is assumed that such children's interest could be transferred to similar programmes developed with African characters, and values primed as instructional materials even at experimental stages. This paper proposes the use of animated objects, and animal characters like tortoise, lion, and spider, which are peculiar to African folklores/folktales, even fictitious characters, can also be created for the same purpose. Ideas from traditional institutions could enrich the narratives while African kingdoms could be used as the domain or environment where the instruction narrative would evolve. In terms of methodology, this study will be advanced from the qualitative angle based on: interviews, content analysis of cartoons/observations. This narrative sets out to understudy the behaviour of young people in relation to their exposure, consumption and preferences for foreign cartoons series. The study draws stimulus from the learning theories postulated by Vygotsky and Bandura among others. This paper proposes that in implementing the early childhood education in African schools curricula in different subject areas, these cartoon series can also become effective pedagogical tools /content cartoons. Findings indicate that poor funding for African cartoonists is at the root of the insufficient cartoons available for African children. The study recommends that cartoonists develop more materials in the proposed African cartoon series and seek for sponsorship for producers who will find in Africa, a large and viable market.

Key word: Indigenous Cartoon, Africa, pedagogical application

Introduction

Education in the 21st century is acknowledged to be more sophisticated than what it used to be decades ago. Several approaches to teaching and learning are emerging especially those that use digital resources and audio visual aids. These approaches are emerging as a result of technological dominance and advancement in the world. Consequently, achieving educational objectives depends enormously on educational technology which today is a vital tool in education. According to Tickton (1970), educational technology is defined as “a systematic way of designing, carrying out

and evaluating the total process of learning and teaching in terms of specific objectives, based on research in human learning and communication and employing a combination of human and non-human resources to bring about more effective instruction”. Pedagogical application of pictorials as teaching aid reinforces learning to a very large extent.

Young children are consistently exposed to pictorials and video stripes both at home and in schools. Considering the fact that children indulge so much in cartoon viewing, research has shown that the interest in cartoons is conspicuously higher than any other

activities children engage in today. There are also numerous cartoons and animated programmes flooding the media network. The popularity of Cartoons among children has given cartoon channels amazing publicity.

Cartoon Network is one of the most patronised cartoon channels. The channel is most often described as the number one destination on television. It is ranked among the most watched cartoon channels in the world. Cartoon network that started transmission in 1992, has been watched in more than 80 million homes in the United States of America and in over 145 countries throughout the world. The various programmes utilize both animal and fictitious characters to engage the viewers.

According to Stabile and Harrison, it is one of the top and supported channels for cable television network. Being a 24/7 channel and broadcasting only cartoons, hence, 68% of its audience are children of the age group of between 2 to 17 years, and the remaining 32% belongs to the age group of between 18 years and above. The children from the age group of 6 to 11 years are the core audience of the Cartoon Network (Stabile and Harrison 2003).

Apart from Cartoon Network, there are other popular cable network Cartoon channels like: Nickelodeon, Cbeebies, Boomerang, Nick Toons, Disney channel, Disney Junior and Jim jam to mention but a few. Numerous evolving cartoon clips and programmes are released worldwide on different media platforms. In spite of the long list, the popularity and the recorded significant number of animated cartoons available worldwide, it is an obvious fact that African animation/cartoons are so insignificant and unpopular.

The various narratives featured in cartoons are usually interesting; with fictitious entertaining characters projected colourfully to catch the fancy of viewers who most times are young persons. The storylines are sometimes drawn from mythological ideas. In spite of all these, it is sad to note that the world around the African child is not sufficiently reflected in the animations they see so regularly. It is based on this reality that Solebo has stated that;

Mythology is empowering. It provides a deeper insight into the

history and psychology of a culture; children in Africa are familiar with cartoons that kids in US and Europe watch. They are less likely to see cartoon characters of African descent and if they do appear, they are normally clichéd and without depth.” (Solebo 2015).

There is a need for the inclusion of African content in the cartoon programmes meant for children.

The early childhood education curriculum has room for the use of audio-visual. However in Africa, the use of cartoons is significantly high and this could accommodate African designed cartoons. It has been observed that, so many languages are going extinct, the stories about great kingdoms in Africa are not preserved, their costumes and dress codes are being replaced subtly, and cultural artefacts are drifting away. How can African ideals and stories be preserved for the future? It is proposed that in developing the much desired African cartoons the selected characters and domain should reflect Africa and the presentation should also be traceable to different African stories and ideals. In African folklore, certain characters are used often e.g. Tortoise (wisdom), Lion (strength), Spider (craft) etc. This strategy will enrich the cartoons dynamically as edutainment.

Improvement on pedagogical approaches is a major focus of this paper especially as it pertains to young African children who are becoming more and more addicted to watching cartoons and also displaying attitudes that show that they are learning tremendously from what they watch and most times they patronise the foreign ideas with so much zeal and interest. Such interest points for children in cartoons can be used as decoy to get their attention to learn. This strategy is suggested on the platform of Africa theatre and performance, utilizing the exigencies in African culture and folklore. This is necessitated by the continuous dwindling of interest in African cultural theatre and the fast growing interest in cartoon viewing amongst children.

There is an ominous need for Africans to tell their stories by themselves for the rest of the world to understand the true African worldview. The global

media network needs to be balanced and enriching with genuine positive storylines about Africa alongside the enormous available narratives about the western world. African cartoon series are therefore required to create this enriching balance.

The Need to Bridge the Gap

In expatiating on what qualifies as an African cartoon, several ideas come to mind. And they include; diversity, recurrent touchstones and imageries peculiar to the African continent. The diversity in Africa provides a pool of resources for the storylines of the cartoons. It is important to draw narratives from the four regions; East, West, North and South Africa, this will create balance even in the face of diversity. Recurrent touchstones are on similitudes in the belief system in Africa, the hierarchy of the gods over man and specials axioms and thought lines peculiar to the people of Africa. In terms of imagery, there are numerous recurrent imagery in the folklore of the Africans. All these peculiarities can enormously enrich African cartoons. Having sufficiently stated that stereotypical cartoon characters excluding African indigenous characters run rampant on the media network. It is also obvious that the media consumption of the African children extensively excludes the African socio-cultural milieu. The main characters featuring in available cartoons globally are white characters with few black or brown “friends”. To say the least, few of these video cartoons promote ‘diversity,’ with respect to African cultures and ideals. On the other hand, diversity in this context is synonymous with “non-white” characters which are mostly not human; which usually portray ideals that the African child cannot be identified with.

Despite the numerous video cartoons, it is almost impossible to make reference to any popular video cartoon that reflects African background and culture. Although some producers have delved into African animations but the popularity of these African animations is near insignificant. It is another thing to have a good story line and a few teasers showing African ideals in video cartoon, it is also another thing to have such video distributed and promoted in the global media network for viewer’s consumption at the same rate with other popular foreign video cartoons. There is however no known African channel on the

cable network Cartoon channels. There is therefore a dire need to bridge this gap.

African performances either in the form of the life performances or recorded in different media are unique. African cultures share common features most of the time. The uniqueness must be well comprehended and interpreted to avoid a misconception that tilts towards negative ratings and criticisms. The diversity and peculiarities of the African performances should be considered as real blessings and avenues for enlightening the younger generations in the continent. The tenacity, zeal and capabilities of the African performers are potential avenues for Africa’s empowerment. This potential could sufficiently provide resources for the much needed African indigenous cartoon series.

Approaches to Learning and Cartoons

Education is vital in the development of a people. The ability of the educator to understand learners goes a long way in determining the learning outcomes reflected on the behaviour of the learner and in selection of resources as well as appropriate teaching aids which may include cartoon. In the education of young children, the play method has also been utilised mainly to enhance the interest of children in learning. From the behaviourist point of view, it can be established that the behaviour of the African child is largely dependent on their exposure and experiences, especially with respect to what they watch (n17ao5-Dox. 9). Cartoon has been recognised as a great means of learning and teaching. Pupils are usually excited at the instance of the use of cartoons in their lessons. Considering the fact that a lot of early learning occurs through pictorials and video expositions; there is the need to develop the ‘junior crowd’ with indigenous contents.

When it comes to education, instructor’s innovative tendencies could aid comprehension and interest of the learners and further improve standards. The creation and use of cartoon for various applications in learning becomes imperative. Part of the educational philosophy of many African countries expects that the societal ideals be transferred via education. If the ideals and culture of Africa must be transmitted to the young ones, then the Children’s interest is the best part to

tackle and focus. They love cartoon then; cartoons should be part of the tools for their enlightenment.

It is not a mean feat to capture young people's attention in classrooms for the purpose of learning, most times engaging pupils as active participants in classes can be problematic. On the other hand, their engagement and attention flow when they watch cartoons is usually very high (n17ao5. 8). More than eighty percent of the early childhood education teachers interviewed in the course of this study confirm this fact. Most early childhood education centres rely on television and foreign cartoons for the introductory stages of learning probably to ease the transition from home to school and also due largely to the factoring the interest of children's love to watch cartoons. The fantasy in colours and sound draws their attention and the communication in these cartoons are tailored to suite children. The character code switch for effective communication at the children's level. It is therefore important for educators to utilize such interest strategically in the classroom; the basic concepts of the different subjects need to be inculcated in cartoons as *concept cartoons*. For over two decades now, concept cartoons are used in classrooms as teaching tools. They are used basically to stimulate argument from learners who usually take-up the role of adjudicators during the lesson, thereby promoting cognitive conflict for formative assessment which culminate in promoting learners interest and their active participation.

According to Brenda and Stuart (1999),

“The purpose for creating them (Concept Cartoons) was as a strategy to elicit learners' ideas, challenge their thinking and support learners in developing their understanding. The response of learners to these Concept Cartoons was encouraging. Primary school students, secondary school students, teachers and student teachers all responded very positively”.

In view of such encouraging development in conceptualizing cartoons for pedagogical application it becomes imperative to mention the need for the inclusion of subjects that can enhance the use of these cartoons to aid learning and teaching in Africa. Enhancing African curriculum will surely aid the responsibility of the continent in the face of globalisation and promoting the relevance of Africans in the sphere of development. Educators have also noticed in recent times that cartoon viewing is one of the most desired hobbies for the majority of children; it has replaced to a large extent other activities. Just as television affects viewer's attitudes most times, Cartoon watching affects the attitude and behaviour of children, including their likes and dislikes, way of talking and conduct. It also has a strong effect on their language and sometimes their way of eating and dressing.

Having observed that one of the most engaging leisure activities that children love is the watching of cartoons and animated programmes on the television, 90% of the early childhood centres visited in the course of this study shows that television is the most utilized resource for young learners and new entrants. It is pertinent at this point to properly understand the meaning and difference between cartoon and animation.

Animation is the process of designing drawing, making layouts and preparation of photographic sequences, which are integrated, in the multimedia and gaming product (India Education page 1). Simply put, is the rapid display of sequential movement of pictures and images of 2-D or 3-D artwork or model positions in order to create an illusion of movements. It is an optical delusion of motion due to the occurrence of persistence of vision; this can be created and established in a number of ways.

The most common method of presenting animation is as a motion picture or video program, although there are several other forms of presenting animations. The term cartoon can be applied to any animated presentation; it is most often used in reference to programs for children, featuring animals, superheroes, the adventures of child protagonists, and other related genres. In this sense, animation has a much broader use than cartoon. Cartoon is a funny film using characters and images that are

drawn rather than real (Cambridge dictionary online 2003).

Animation could be very useful among various content areas in the education industry especially with respect to the development of the child's cognitive skills and other behavioural patterns.

Approaches and Uses of Foreign Cartoons

African schools utilize numerous pictorials and video cartoons in engaging their pupils. Trips to schools especially the early Childhood Learning Centres like Crèches and early primary schools reveal that western cartoon series are significantly used to engage and enlighten young folks. As a result of this, it is observed that young Africans are exposed to contents that are subtly indoctrinating them to foreign ideologies, terminologies vocabularies and attitudes. The behaviour of these children is therefore transfigured to the pattern of the content of these cartoons. They definitely learn from these exposures, however, they should also learn about their immediate environment and culture in order to become knowledgeable about themselves. Pedagogical relevance of cartoons can become a turning point in the improvement of the content of education in the early childhood education. "Cartoons can play a significant role in highlighting stories that have delighted and informed generations for centuries especially with children" (Solebo 2015).

This paper therefore projects African video cartoons basically for pedagogical use. Children irrespective of their age or background should be exposed to view cartoons with diverse characters from different cultural settings in order to balance their view about the world. The African child has been constantly exposed to imported cartoons that have little or nothing to do with them, especially in terms of ethnic and cultural issues. Young children are constantly being bombarded with negative and patronizing images of Africa, and generally grow up with unbalanced ideas and confusing mind-sets, which affect learning outcomes and behaviour. This problem sometimes contributes to the negative impression created about the continent. The need for the incorporation of indigenous African cartoons in pedagogical approaches is hereby solicited.

Area of Need for African Cartoons

(1) **Language Preservation:** many languages in Africa could be said to be facing extinction as a result of the importation of almost all aspects of the African child education. No doubt, the education of Africans is more foreign in content, but if the language of Africa is tenacious in any sense, then cartoons could be used to develop materials for such learning. Cartoons could help in this era of campaign for the preservation of languages in Africa. As suggested by Chonchaiya & Pinksananond (2008) that "learning communicate is one of the major developmental milestones during early childhood. Language acquisition is an intricate process that involves auditory, linguistic, cognitive and environmental factors." This makes it imperative for more work in language preservation and to be developed in line with the needs of the child and society.

(2) **Morality/Virtue:** the virtue of African ideals and cultural heritage could be preserved and also reduce the dominance of foreign ideals. Virtues like respect, communal concern greeting etc. may be said to have been seriously reduced and replaced with that depicted with the western culture. The creation of African cartoons from different socio cultural milieu can really be helpful at this point in time.

(3) **Enhancing Methods Digitalize of Teaching and Learning:** to cope with children, especially those with disability in the classroom setting, cartoons can bridge the gap between them and other children; it can be replayed over and over again for emphasis and assimilation. It can also help inculcate values at the foundation stage in the African children, the new trend in global digitalized learning and keep them abreast with the current trends. Cartoons videos are not meant to replace face to face interaction with people (teachers) as the best source of learning for infants. Diener et al (2008: 418)

Rating African Indigenous Cartoon

A review in today's world of video cartoon series reveals that there are little or limited information on the existence of African cartoon series. It is common knowledge that during the various African performances and movie awards ceremonies, the place for Animation is almost nonexistence. How can this be

when it is a known fact that enormous quantities of productions are churned out of the African movie milieu? Since the various entertainment awards usually consider the ratings and voting form viewers of such programmes there is no awards for animation because it is not available.

A survey of the list of categories for such awards in Africa especially the movie awards however reveal the insignificance of the Animation category. At the foreign scene, the Academy awards since 2001 have been recognising; the best animated feature in their award ceremonies. This can be considered as one of the catalysts for the huge number of video cartoon series originating from the foreign scene as animators are recognised and given credit for their works. A search on the world's most popular video cartoon list and most watched cartoon list etc. reveals that African cartoon series are not so popular. According to Christal (2016), "Its common knowledge that children gain pride when they see positive images of themselves during their early years. African and African-American children don't have many opportunities to see themselves when watching cartoons." This is not encouraging, considering the high tech era we live in today.

Developing a Curriculum for Pedagogical Application

Pedagogy here implies the teaching and learning process for younger minds. It refers broadly to the deliberate process of cultivating development within a given culture and society. In respect to education, *the use of cartoon could have several advantages:*

- (i) *Ability to give life to boring, complicated subject areas and promotion of learner's interest.*
- (ii) *Prolong attention span.*
- (iii) *Enhance student's communicative and linguistic competences.*

Learning can be classified into different domains and the taxonomy of learning as propounded by Benjamin Blooms (1956), highlights three domains of learning as; the cognitive domain (brain work), the affective domain (feelings /personal perception) and the psychomotor domain (physical /hand and legs operations). The use of cartoon for pedagogy has the

potential of affecting two out of the three learning domains maximally when properly harnessed and can sometimes prompt the psychomotor domain reasonably.

Pedagogy has three (3) basic components: (i) Curriculum. (ii) Methodology. (iii) Socialization technique. These three (3) components could be considered while producing these cartoons which technically should be low pace, showing fewer frames of not more than 40 per second. Low pace videos are capable of reducing the negative effect of television on young people. The use of video cartoons tilts towards technological advancement. The world has become a global village, adopting technological approach in learning especially electronically, pushes education further and updated. *Cartoons could become excellent teaching tools for online process because there are not only adding humour to the topic, but there can also illustrate the idea in a memorable way.* (Joseph Giunta)

Some scholarly opinions are worth highlighting at this point in time for a broader analysis of this subject matter; the quotations from some great writers in this area are x-rayed herewith. Young children throughout the world are surrounded by opportunities to develop and use emergent literacy skills like listening, speaking, reading, and writing. These opportunities are as diverse as the language, cultures, and peoples they represent and acknowledge the many linguistic, cognitive, and socio-emotional resources available to young children in their daily lives. Opportunities found in every culture of the world include watching, listening, and using language Feldman (1980).

Considering the fact that animations and cartoons are usually a source of education, their quality and quantity play a critical role in emergent literacy skills development, which lay the foundation for adolescent and adult language use and thinking as documented in a large and robust international research base (DeTemple, 2001; Dickinson & Newman, 2006; Hart & Risley, 1995; Newman & Dickinson, 2004; Purcell-Gates & Dahl, 1991; Scarborough, 1998; Senechal,

Ouellette, & Rodney, 2006; Snow, Burns, & Griffin, 1998; van Kleeck, 2003; Whitehurst & Lonigan, 1998). Today, in social communication research, the impact of cartoons has gained a new status. Animation is used to convey the messages to target audience, e.g. in marketing and learning (Ginmann, 2003)

In terms of behaviour of African children who are exposed to the numerous foreign cartoons the opinions of Vygotsky and Bandura are apt in explaining the outcome; Vygotsky's assumption on how children learn is centred on who and what they are exposed to, the community plays major role in learning as well as people around them affects their world view. It is deduced that Vygotsky encourages leisure as very important for learning as it leads to abstract thought, which later leads to higher mental functions. He describes this mental capacity in zones known as zone of proximal development. He believes that children with higher zones will do better in school. Zones of proximal development aids problem solving skills. This is determined by skills/tasks which children can perform independently.

Bandura's behaviour modelling theory on the other hand believes that Behaviour modelling occurs when individuals observe and imitate other individuals. The individual and the environment influences each other in what he terms "reciprocal determinism". He posits that observation and interaction is key and that psychological processes including imagery and language are linked to behaviour and creates learning.

In children especially, research has shown that there are different variables that have effects on them. Variables such as liking and disliking of cartoon characters, based on their gender, accessories and costumes they use, physical attractiveness, age, intelligence, anti and pro-social behaviours and over goodness and badness (Klein and Shiffman, 2006).

Today, mother tongue is greatly affected by the different linguistic expressions which are being presented on television. Likewise, children also are affected to a large extent by the different linguistic terms presented on television in their favourite dramas and cartoons. Kottak believes that television programs and all types of cartoons and animated movies are the main factors which are playing a key role in culturalization of American children (Kottak 1990). How can a continent where millions of home videos are produced at very short notice be unable to produce video cartoons that project their rich cultural ideas? The vulnerability of the world to the one sided report about Africa and Africans can be reduced significantly when video strips and pictorials that highlight the positive sides of the continent are utilized. It is not only to teach but also to preserve the ideals and cultures of African. No matter how expensive this venture might appear at any point it must be noted that the economic rewards that African indigenous cartoon serves producers is not questionable.

The population of viewers in Africa is quite encouraging and producers who venture into this area of need in Africa will be happy at the end of the day. It is common knowledge that from the 1990s to 2000s Nigerian Nollywood has become the second largest film industry in the world in number of annual film production placing it ahead of the United States and behind only India's Bollywood as at 2013 the Nigerian film industry was worth over NG853.9 billion and about US\$ 5.1 billion. (UNESCO 2013)

More producers should emerge from the tertiary institutions in Africa, this is necessary in order to minimize the bottleneck in the production of movies in Africa. Examining the education system becomes very essential as Socrates rightly stated that "an unexamined life is not worth living". On that note therefore, questions that will require genuine answers on this platform include:

- Are Theatre and media effective platforms for the propagation of the ideals of a people and society?
- How do we apply the answers to the African context?
- Are they necessary tools in production of African indigenous cartoons?

- Are African Tertiary institutions ready to introduce and update programmes that will make African performances relevant in the 21st century?

Animation is a major requirement that can aid the production of African indigenous video cartoons. It is time to look inward and do the needful. The African story should be told by Africans, especially with the right modalities on the media network. Teaching children should be done meticulously to bring about the right learning outcome and behaviour, using indigenous cartoons to enlighten African children is a strategy worth embracing. One of the most inspiring educational slogans ever used is “If children cannot learn the way we teach, then we teach the way they learn”- (Angel’s Specialist School International Tema, Ghana). Let African children be taught the way they will understand.

These opinions are evidences that the intentions of this paper are not new because much research has been undertaken in this area. This paper here-by opens up more prospects in the frontiers of learning for the development of indigenous African cartoon series for teaching and learning.

Recommendations

This paper therefore makes a passionate appeal to all practitioners in the growing African movie industry to begin to create indigenous cartoon series for children. ‘The slow pace’ video format is hereby recommended in the production process, as fast-paced programmes are not so good for young children’s brains. According to research, it appears that children ‘may not concentrate and focus very well after watching fast-paced programming’- Cohen and Gupta (2011). This paper therefore suggests the production of indigenous cartoons for pedagogical uses. This paper also suggests that these indigenous cartoons be produced as ‘slow paced’ animations to avoid any adverse effect on the minds of the young viewers. In the production of these cartoons, producers are admonished to work hand in hand with experienced educators in order to ensure compliance with the proposals and for maximum impact and results. This paper therefore advocates the following:

- (1) The mass media globally should be promoting African Cartoons.
- (2) African plays (literature) can become the springboard for indigenous African cartoon production. The need for translating them into cartoons audio-visuals is serious.
- (3) African brands that market children products should help promote different African Cartoons as children relate to those brands and would easily relate to the indigenous cartoon characters they promote.
- (4) Stake holders in education should invest in this project and encourage creativity and quality cartoon series that depicts African ideals even as instructional materials.
- (5) African cartoons should as a matter of urgency reasonably replace western ones in African Crèches and other Early Childhood Education Centres.

Conclusion

One established area of interest for children is video cartoons; they can be subtly primed for teaching different subject areas in education with the aim of enhancing learning and teaching, using African kingdoms and ideologies as the main domain of the content of such productions.

The interest and excitement of these suggestions may not see the light of day if other approaches in theatre education are not revolutionised. The dream for the development of African Indigenous Cartoon Series could remain a tall one if the Curriculum of Theatre Arts and Media related areas are not overhauled. Thanks to the existing curriculum, which have produced great achievers in the industry. The time has come for Africans to wake up to the challenges of speed at which the world is moving digitally, even though we cannot run as fast as our western counterparts, at least let the movement begin. Relevance to practice is considered as the motivating force for any training aimed at outstanding results.

How many universities offering theatre and media have detailed courses in Animation? Is Animation excluded from the curriculum of theatre and media in the western world? It is time to examine our

training and education “An unexamined life is not worth living” (Apology 38a5-6).

Having established the common reality that the 21st century children all over the globe are actively obsessed with television viewing, especially video cartoon series or animations, they have become conversant with the numerous cartoon characters and the qualities of such programmes on the media network. The African indigenous cartoons should therefore not be produced with lesser definitions or qualities both in the audio and visual aspects in order to sustain the pulse of the children’s interest. Just as African children have been enjoying foreign cartoons this paper envisages and advocates that the new African based cartoons should also captivate the interest of children outside Africa. This calls for the involvement of qualified producers both in Africa and in the Diaspora. As children mix up and socialize, references are made to the cartoon programmes and characters that they find interesting. This has contributed to popular traits and use of language. Popular sing along and rhymes have also been learnt from cartoons. To a great extent children learn so much from cartoon without even knowing. Children learn new sounds, shapes and colors with the help of cartoons; watching cartoons could inspire children to dance, get excited and even develop imaginative language only known to them. African Parents must be truly delighted to see their children learn concepts that are familiar to them on the television.

Developing indigenous African cartoons could help Africans do the following and more:

1. Teach children about the important value systems, ideals and the culture of their continent.
2. Teach children about languages and communication patterns expected of them.
3. Teach behavioral patterns and positive character development.
4. Teach geographical and constitutional leadership details about African kingdom from a variety of ages.
5. Teach dress sense and expose the rich costumes and accessories of the people of Africa.

Developing African Indigenous cartoons for teaching young Africans is a venture worth investing in and the large African population is a positive news for its marketing and profitability. Producing African cartoons is possible.

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